

Sea-Truth Experiments on Acoustic Doppler Current Profiling Systems

by

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Abstract

Two experiments were conducted in the summer of 1982 with "off-the-shelf" AMETEK-Straza DCP4400 acoustic Doppler current profiling systems. The first experiment compared a bottom-mounted upward-looking 300 kHz system against moored current measuring systems. Conductivity-temperature-depth (CTD) profiles, water samples, and meteorological data were collected to augment the current measurements and aid in the interpretation of the acoustic Doppler measurements.

The second experiment involved real-time comparisons between the downward-looking 115 kHz acoustic profiling system installed on the NOAA Ship RESEARCHER and current measurements made with an EG&G - Vector Measuring Current Meter (VMCM) lowered from the ship while on station off the coast of Florida.

This paper presents the results from both experiments along with a discussion on the performance of the AMETEK-Straza DCP4400 systems.

Introduction

The National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) has been involved with the development of acoustic remote sensing techniques for several years. The National Ocean Service (NOS) of NOAA purchased an AMETEK-Straza DCP4400 system in 1981 for use in a bottom-mounted configuration to establish a long-term installation of an acoustic measurement system capable of providing real-time information. A shipboard system was also purchased by NOS in 1981 and was configured to make vertical profile current measurements from an underway ship. The development of the technology for shipboard applications is to provide systems (eventually automated for ships-of-opportunity) to measure parameters associated with heat transport in the upper ocean in support of a national climate program. Field tests were performed by NOS on both of these systems to define their measurement capabilities. The following is a description of the experiments and the results obtained.

Chesapeake Bay Experiment

In August 1982, an intensive field experiment was conducted in the Chesapeake Bay by the NOS. The major objective of the experiment was to investigate the performance of an AMETEK-Straza acoustic profiler in a bottom-mounted configuration. Seventeen conventional current meters were deployed, and numerous ancillary measurements were taken to provide "sea truth" measurements for defining the performance of the acoustic profiler.

System Design

The acoustic profiler tested in the experiment was an AMETEK-Straza DCP4400/300, which uses a 4-beam acoustic transducer in a Janus configuration. The system transmits 300 kHz acoustic pulses (pings) along each of 4 beams which are tilted 30° from the vertical, have a 3° beamwidth, and are mutually orthogonal (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Conceptual diagram of the DCP4400 profiler provided courtesy of AMETEK-Straza.

Acoustic scatterers suspended in the water reflect a portion of this acoustic energy back towards the transducer; the motion of these scatterers along the beams result in a frequency shift in the reflected signal proportional to their velocity. The DCP4400 system processes the acoustic return signals for each beam in short segments (bins) and provides a measure of this frequency shift at fixed intervals along the beams. A Hewlett Packard HP-85 then acquires the data, determines the horizontal component of current in each bin for each beam by applying simple trigonometry and computes the mean and standard deviation of multiple pings. The HP-85 also provides operational control of the DCP4400. During this experiment the system was operated with a 3.2 ms transmit pulse width, a 2.4 ms binwidth which provided a measurement of current every 1.6 m in the water column.

Experiment Design

The experiment was conducted in the Chesapeake Bay near Solomons Island, Md. The site was located on the west side of the shipping channel in 18m of water where the bottom was relatively flat. A review of existing data from the site indicated the flow characteristics during August would be mainly tidal and well stratified due to low salinity water from the upper bay flowing over heavier, higher salinity water from the lower bay.

Seventeen conventional current meters were deployed on five moorings which were placed along the axis of the Bay (Figure 2).

The NOS and NOS#36 moorings (Figure 2) contained Grundy Environmental Systems model 9021 rotor current meters sampling every 10 minutes. The MMI mooring consisted of a Marsh McBirney Inc. model 585 electromagnetic current meter programmed to burst sample the currents (1 sample/sec) for 1 minute each hour and an Applied Microsystems Ltd. model 750 water level gage. The CBI mooring contained 8 modified Endeco model 174 current meters which sampled every 2 minutes and an Aanderaa RCM-4 which sampled every 10 minutes. This mooring was designed to provide the vertical resolution necessary to evaluate the DCP4400 profiler. The DCP4400 transducer and junction box was platform mounted and a EG&G Vector Measuring Current Meter (VMCM) mooring was mounted torsionally rigid to the platform; the VMCM compass provided the orientation of the DCP4400 relative to magnetic north. These two instruments were hardwired to the R/V LAIDLAY which was in a four-point mooring near the test site during the entire experiment. The DCP4400 system computed a 4 minute vector average of currents every 6 minutes which consisted of 120 pings. The DCP4400 was not operated for short periods during the experiment to accommodate tests of other acoustic systems which operated at similar frequencies.

All current meters used in the experiment were calibrated before and after the experiment and measurement uncertainties were computed for each. In addition to the current meter moorings, a series of ancillary measurements were collected which included wind speed and direction, conductivity and temperature profiles, and water samples which were analyzed for particle size distribution and total suspended load. An analysis of the relationship between acoustic volume backscatter intensity from the DCP4400 and the properties of the water column is underway. A report is in preparation which will describe the physical oceanography of the test site during the experiment.

Experiment Results

A 30-minute averaging interval was chosen for data analysis to filter instrument noise and accommodate instrument comparisons since it was the least common denominator for the various instrument sampling rates.

The vector means for a 3-day time series, Julian days 233 to 236, excluding the times when the DCP4400 was either not operating or operating in other than a 6-minute cycle, were computed for each of the current measurements (Table 1). A comparison of the DCP4400 measurements with the sea truth data in bins 3 through 7 indicates general agreement at the various levels. Vector magnitude comparisons of 3-day averages generally show a 3 cm/s difference between the DCP4400 and the seatruth. A similar comparison of direction measurements show a scatter of approximately $\pm 4^\circ$ in the upper water column; comparisons in the lower layers below the pycnocline are not as good. However, variations between current meters in the lower layers are also large and dependent on depth. Comparing the standard deviations of the North-South component of flow, which is the predominant axis of the tidal signal, shows correlation to better than 2 cm/s between the DCP4400 and the current meters.

Figure 2. Configuration drawing of the Chesapeake Bay Experiment.

Figure 3 is a three-day vector "stick" plot of the sea truth and DCP4400 measurements. The sea truth measurements depict the complex flow regime of the test site where the tidal inflow occurs mainly below the pycnocline and the outflow is mostly above the pycnocline. This flow pattern resulted in vertical shear of the horizontal current in the order of 4 cm/s/m during portions of the experiment.

Bin 9 is located near the surface and appears to follow the wind signal (upper left) with a tidal signal superimposed. This is the flow characteristic which one would expect in the near-surface; however, definitive statements cannot be made regarding this bin because no sea truth measurements were made in the near-surface.

The direction of the vectors for bin 8 correlate with the sea truth but the magnitudes are consistently low. This is caused by the surface reflection from the vertical side lobe of the transducer which is large in comparison to the backscatter signal from along the main beam. The DCP4400 computes the mean value of the frequency spectra for determination of velocity magnitude. For near-surface measurements, the main lobe backscatter Doppler signal is averaged with the side lobe surface reflection which has zero Doppler shift resulting in a reduction in computed magnitude.

Bins 3 through 7 agree with the sea truth for both magnitude and direction.

Figure 3. Three-day vector "stick" plot of the sea truth and DCP4400 measurements.

Bins 1 and 2 of the DCP4400 could not be correlated with the sea truth. Near-field transducer effects, mechanical ringing of the transducer and side lobe reflections from the VMCM current meter are possible causes for the lack of agreement with the sea truth.

Figure 4 is a North-South vector comparison (tidal flow axis) of Bins 3 through 7 with the corresponding modified Endeco current meters. This comparison indicates the DCP4400 system follows these sea truth measurements, however, its speed magnitudes are generally higher.

Table 1

MEAN STATISTICS
DAYS 233 TO 235 MINUS GAPS

Current Meter	Height above bottom (M)	U (cm/s)	U-Std dev	V (cm/s)	V-Std dev	Vector Magnitude	Vector Direction
E#187	14.9	2.9	6.2	-9.6	26.0	10.1	163.1
E#061	12.2	0.3	3.7	-8.7	23.3	8.7	178.3
G#035	12.2	1.6	5.2	-7.6	22.4	7.8	168.0
E#192	10.6	1.9	5.8	-5.8	21.3	6.1	161.5
E#149	9.6	1.6	6.9	-2.0	21.5	2.6	141.3
G#034	9.6	-1.1	6.9	1.1	24.3	1.6	314.4
E#191	8.5	0.3	6.0	2.8	22.4	2.8	7.0
E#076	7.5	-2.9	6.7	5.4	24.0	6.1	331.2
E#189	6.5	-1.5	7.2	6.5	27.4	6.7	346.7
G#063	5.5	1.2	8.2	6.2	32.1	6.3	11.1
VMCM	5.5	-1.8	8.1	6.7	31.7	7.0	345.0
G#062	5.5	1.1	8.2	5.4	31.6	5.5	11.8
AA3143	2.4	0.3	8.2	-3.5	27.6	3.5	175.8
G#060	1.5	-0.9	5.1	-2.2	19.0	2.4	203.1
<u>DCP 4400</u>							
BINA8	15.0	1.2	10.3	-5.0	17.0	5.2	166.5
BINA7	13.4	-0.4	12.9	-11.8	24.4	11.8	181.8
BINA6	11.8	0.2	11.6	-8.8	24.5	8.8	178.6
BINA5	10.2	1.3	11.7	-1.9	23.8	2.3	145.5
BINA4	8.6	2.0	11.5	5.7	22.3	6.0	18.9
BINA3	7.0	1.4	10.4	8.6	20.8	8.7	9.1

Figure 4. North-South vector comparison of Sea-Truth vs. the DCP4400.

Analysis and Conclusions

Normally, measurement system accuracies are determined in a laboratory by comparison to standards over a selected measurement range. However, laboratory facilities do not presently exist where a DCP4400 can be calibrated. Therefore, realizing the limitations to field intercomparisons, an attempt to determine the accuracy of the DCP4400 using a least squares analysis technique was made. The modified Endeco current meters were selected for comparison to each bin and only the north-south component of flow was used for the analysis.

Least squares analysis of the DCP4400 data set for the 3 days versus the commensurate modified Endeco data set at each depth indicated the DCP4400 gain is approximately 10 percent higher than the modified Endeco and yields a residual standard error (RSE) of 5.3 cm/s. If the same least squares analysis is performed on the appropriate Grundy versus Endeco data

set, it indicates the Grundy gain is also 5 percent higher than the Endeco and the RSE is 4.0 cm/s. A Grundy versus VMCM analysis shows no gain difference, and a RSE of 5.5 cm/s.

It is concluded that the DCP4400 performed within our capability to define "sea truth." Unfortunately, as with all field intercomparisons, our ability to define performance is limited by the measurement uncertainties resulting from the instruments used and the variability of the environment. From this experiment it was determined that the DCP4400 30-minute averages have a 95 percent confidence of better than 12.5 cm/s and the 3-day averages are better than 2.5 cm/s.

Florida Current Experiment

On September 29, 1982, a limited experiment was conducted in the Florida Current by the National Ocean Service and the Atlantic Oceanographic and Meteorological Laboratory (AOML) aboard the NOAA Ship RESEARCHER. The objective of the experiment was to compare the results of current measurements from a VMCM lowered over the side of the ship to the current measurements made from a DCP4400 acoustic profiler. Fourteen measurements were made at six depths for the comparison.

System Design

The acoustic profiler tested was an AMETEK-Straza DCP4400/115 with an acoustic transducer mounted to the ship's hull. The system is similar to that which was described previously except it operates at 115 kHz and has only three beams. The pulse length used was 9.6 ms with a depth resolution of 6.4 meters (bin width).

The VMCM was lowered over the side of the ship to the desired depth so that it measured in the middle of an acoustic depth bin. The depths chosen to sample at were 20, 40, 50, 60, 100, and 150 meters. The measurements were made from the ship after it had hove to in the Florida Current and were made in calm conditions, thus no corrections for ship speed, roll, pitch, or yaw needed to be made in the measurements.

Experimental Results

Both the VMCM and DCP4400 sampled every second and computed one-minute averages of north and east components of velocity. The VMCM was held in the specified depth bin for at least 11 one-minute averages. The measurements were then used to compute a mean and a 95 percent confidence limit for each 11 minute average. These results were plotted in a scatter diagram, Figures 5 and 6, for the north and east velocity components respectively. Each point also has the 95 percent confidence limit for the speed estimates shown as the length of the horizontal (STRAZA) and vertical (VMCM) lines of the cross.

Figure 5, the east component of velocity, shows good agreement with a correlation greater than 0.95 between the two devices at relatively low measurement speeds. Figure 6, the north component of velocity, shows excellent agreement between the two instruments over a range of 5 to 100 cm/s, with a correlation of over 0.99.

Figure 5. VMCM vs DCP4400/115 East component of flow.

Figure 6. VMCM vs DCP4400/115 North component of flow.

Conclusion

The results from this basic Florida Current experiment demonstrate that the DCP4400 provides a good measure of the current profile. It was determined that the 11-minute average of velocity has a 95 percent confidence (from a least squares analysis) of better than 14 cm/s for the north component using VMCM as the independent variable. Further performance information will soon be available as the profiler is now in use by AOML for current profiling from the ship while underway.

Recommendations

The results of these tests show the remote acoustic Doppler measurement technique for current profiling has potential for use in many applications. However, the performance of these systems over their full range of operating conditions remains unknown. It is recommended that users of these systems remain cautious of data acquired and that a concerted effort be maintained by all users to establish a performance data base. It is further recommended that continued investigation is required in the following areas:

- Signal processing techniques, particularly with regard to spectral analysis of the returned Doppler signal
- Improved near-surface measurements which requires improving transducer design to reduce side lobes.
- Continued investigation of the interpretation and potential applications of volume backscatter measurements of these acoustic systems.

-- Define the long-term performance and reliability of the acoustic systems over a wider range of environments and in an area where the sea truth can be better defined.

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